

Methods of physical education and improving the health levels of student youth

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Abstract: The article discusses the issues of increasing the health levels of student youth in the process of physical education and sports. At the same time, the study of a set of research results on the body of students, the formation of a healthy lifestyle through physical education, physical training and physical development of modern youth. Thus, the importance of physical education for students for general physical training, primarily for promoting health.

Key words: Physical education, health, preparation, development, student, sport, process, body, preparation, condition, youth, healthy image.

Introduction

Health is an invaluable asset not only for every person, but also for the entire society. The purpose of physical education in universities is to promote the preparation of harmoniously developed, highly qualified specialists.

In the process of studying at a university in the course of physical education, the following tasks are envisaged:

- nurturing in students high moral, volitional and physical qualities, readiness for highly productive work;
 - maintaining and strengthening the health of students, promoting the correct formation and comprehensive development of the body, maintaining high performance throughout the entire period of study;
 - comprehensive physical training of students;
 - professionally applied physical training of students, taking into account the characteristics of their future work activity;
 - acquisition by students of the necessary knowledge on the basics of theory, methodology and organization of physical education and sports training, preparation for work as public instructors, coaches and judges;
 - improving the sports skills of students;
 - instilling in students the conviction of the need to regularly engage in physical education and sports.
- The physical education program provides for the direct involvement of each student in physical education and sports as the most effective means of promoting health. It is the valeological aspects in the structure of the physical education system for student youth that constitute its priority essence. However, it can be noted that in the practice of physical education there is not always work to determine the level of students' health and its control. It is known that it is the level of individual somatic health that determines the safe zone of intensity of physical activity during physical exercise and is a criterion for the effectiveness of these activities.

When forming physical education and increasing the physical fitness of students, it is necessary to take into account the state of health and level of physical fitness, as well as a number of socio-economic and environmental problems.

Adjustment of traditional methods in physical education is necessary, especially with a reduction in teaching hours for physical education classes. It is necessary to orient students to physical education

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classes with individual predisposition, availability of physical activity in a certain direction. This is a good motivation for doing independent physical exercises in your free time.

One of the main tasks of the management structures of higher educational institutions is to organize the educational process in such a way that the student not only does not lose his health resources, but also replenishes them. In this regard, the organization of the healthcare system is currently focused on motivating the preservation of health in the consciousness and behavior of young people. The central problem is to overcome the contradiction between the potential of personal physical culture, the level of social knowledge, cultural heritage in the field of activity related to physical education, the improvement of a young person, on the one hand, and the level of individual knowledge of students in this area, on the other. That is why, at present, the place of physical culture in the value system of a student's personality does not correspond to its importance as one of the most important indicators of the general culture of student youth.

The goal of the educational process should be the creation of an educational environment aimed at the harmonious development of the individual, the formation of a system of value orientations and the establishment of an active life position of students based on positive motivation for self-development and self-improvement, as well as interest in supporting a healthy lifestyle, creating conditions for scientific, creative, physical development of the student as the basis for the formation of a healthy lifestyle.

For a targeted discussion of current issues of a healthy lifestyle for students, a special topic of abstracts is proposed, which was an integral part of the theoretical section in the discipline "Physical Culture". During practical classes, skills and abilities of health-saving behavior are consolidated, skills of self-monitoring of physical condition, self-insurance techniques when performing physical exercises are formed, and optimal motor modes are determined using specific examples.

Physical education is a pedagogical process that is aimed at improving the forms and functions of the human body, the formation of motor skills, related knowledge skills, as well as the development of physical qualities. Physical education is connected with other aspects of education - moral, aesthetic, production, labor.

One of the most important conditions for raising a healthy generation is a culture of human health, instilled from early childhood. In modern conditions of an ever-accelerating pace of life and increasing tension in social relations, health is becoming one of the main conditions for the success of any person. Everyone understands how important it is, starting from a very early age, to instill in children an active attitude towards their own health, to create a culture of health that includes various aspects of human existence.

The main components of human health are complete mental, physical and social well-being directly related to his socio-economic and cultural-ethnic environment. The low level of health and general physical development of many students, as well as its further decline in the learning process, pose a serious problem today, therefore, in the educational process it is necessary to organize independent work aimed at improving physical development and maintaining health.

Independent work included in the learning process is work that is performed without the direct participation of the teacher, but according to his instructions and in the time specially provided for this. At the same time, students consciously strive to achieve their goal, showing their efforts and expressing in one form or another the results of their mental and physical actions.

In the process of cultivating interest in physical exercise, it comes from the essence of the general system of educational work, as well as from the characteristics of age. The conditions for training and

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education of students, determined by our reality, determine in turn the interests of students in this or that activity and contribute to the formation of personality.

One of the main conditions for cultivating interest in physical exercise is active physical activity, because the connection between theory and practice is one of the decisive factors for a physically comprehensive, harmoniously developed person. The main feature of the condition of active motor activity is that the development of interest in physical exercise occurs on their basis, since during these classes the student is not only a simple performer of certain physical exercises and tasks, but he himself actively participates in the physical culture life of the team, applies and uses various physical exercises to develop certain moral traits and qualities.

The work on physical education and education does not consist of calls and slogans on issues of physical culture and sports, but in the creation of physical culture and sports, tourism, in which the student would participate in the physical education, mass and sports life of his team. Forming an attitude towards a healthy lifestyle is the most important task of the state, since lifestyle is a determining factor of health. Creating your own healthy lifestyle system is an extremely long process and can last a lifetime.

Feedback from the changes occurring in the body as a result of following a healthy lifestyle does not work immediately; the positive effect of switching to a rational lifestyle is sometimes delayed for years. Unfortunately, very often students only try the transition itself, but without getting quick results, they return to their previous lifestyle. In such situations, when students have bad habits, and their health deteriorates during the learning process, taking the path of a healthy lifestyle is very important. Often, one of the reasons for the decrease in the level of condition and physical fitness is the unresolved problem of an individual approach, which leads to low efficiency of physical education and, as a consequence of this objective factor, to weak interest in physical exercise, low level of physical education literacy, underdeveloped motivation and needs for mastering values of physical culture. The implementation of individual and typological approaches contributes to the development of intellectual and cognitive abilities, increasing interest in physical exercise, cultivating positive emotions, reducing mental fatigue and emotional stress, and increasing student performance.

It is known that the effectiveness of physical education is associated with prompt diagnosis of the physical condition of students. Only having information about the level of physical fitness, the individual abilities of the body to perform the load, can one determine the content of classes and make the required adjustments to it. Unfortunately, diagnostics often comes down to testing students at the beginning and end of the academic year and is only of an ascertaining nature. The data does not receive further pedagogical interpretation, and this is no coincidence, since in order to analyze the test results and draw conclusions about possible pedagogical measures, the teacher needs too much time. The use of software and technological complexes designed to solve problems of assessing the physical status of athletes, organizing and storing data for subsequent analyzes and individual recommendations for correcting health and physique will make it possible to reduce this time and increase the information content of test results.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we can conclude that the constant attention paid to the development of sports in the country is based on the goal of raising a comprehensively healthy and spiritually rich generation. Observing the above principles, in the conditions of an educational institution, a process of educational material and educational activities is carried out that reveal the essence of the main components of health and a healthy lifestyle through organizing the interaction of participants in the pedagogical

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process, in which values, health ideals and an understanding of the need to improve one's own health are formed.

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